

The Relationship Between Green Marketing Adoption and Business Size: Evidences from e-commerce sector in Albania

Eleni KALEMAJ

*Lecturer at the Department of Business Administration at University of New York Tirana/ PhD Candidate at Mediterranean University, Albania elenijarazi@unyt.edu.al

Abstract

The development of information technologies and the internet has caused one of the most significant changes in the business environment over the last decade. Companies have evolved to adapt to a digital environment influenced by internet business models and digital marketing techniques. More and more firms and enterprises around the world are responding to consumer higher sensitivity regarding the protection of environment and need by either embracing circular economy models or adopting strategies of green marketing. These strategies may range from eco-friendlier supply chains, green packaging, environmentally friendly products or promoting broader efforts to reduce environmental impact. The current paper analyzes such strategies by using background cases that inform the primary Albanian case, to understand how fast the Albanian e-commerce companies are catching up with this environmentally friendly business models and how green marketing may help. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of green marketing adoption among Albanian E-businesses and to investigate the impact of business size on green marketing adoption. The research model was tested with national survey data collected from Albanian e-commerce firms of different business size. The present study opens broad horizons for the exploration of green marketing strategies in the e-business proactiveness and the impact on e-business agility in responding to environmental uncertainty. This study shows that future-oriented companies can profit economically while reducing their negative environmental impact.

Keywords: E-business, green marketing, sustainable marketing, business size, Albania

Jel Code: M, O, Q

I. Introduction

Sustainability and environmental issues are among the most pressing concerns for modern humanity, governments, and environmentally conscious consumers (Hsu et al, 2013). It should be noted that business activities, including marketing, play a role in enhancing sustainable development. According to Polonsky (1997), marketing as a business function must ensure that future generations' ability to meet their needs and desires is not jeopardized. On the other hand, Robert (2011) contends that sustainable development necessitates sustainable marketing strategies that are both competitive and environmentally sustainable. As a result, marketing's role in development has been significantly reorganized (Kotler, 2019).

In recent years, economic performance has needed to be balanced against environmental and social performance. Within the input process of innovation generation, activities related to demonstrating the resources on a country's requirement to produce goods and services, as well as increasing unwanted products in the form of waste and pollution, are included.

Albania was ranked in the 79 places among with 118 country that had the worst air quality in 2021 (IQAir, 2022). According to the report published in 2020 by the "European Environment Agency", Albania has second highest rate of pollution related with deaths in Europe. Albania found itself second on the "worst countries" list, after Bosnia and Herzegovina. Noted in the report Albania has 23% of recorded deaths due to environmental matters, it is 10 percentage points higher than the European average. Factors impacting the big disparity include lower sanitation levels and higher exposure to waste substances that are detrimental to health and life expectancy. The Numbeo Pollution Index ranked Tirana as the third most polluted city in Europe in January 2020. Despite the fact that Albanian's national strategy has focused on promoting green growth and sustainable development, it has only achieved a limited level of success due to a lack of implementation. This is due to the lack of good governance and integrated partnerships aimed at mutual growth in the economy, environment, and quality of life. Furthermore, due to a lack of collaboration, Albanian public policy intervention is ineffective in extending the socioeconomic benefits of green practices. As a result, it places severe constraints on business and policymakers in terms of eco-innovation policy and strategy.

As a result, there is a growing need to transition to a green economy for eco-friendly driven innovation, also known as eco-innovation. This includes new products, processes, and management solutions that have a lower environmental impact. There is a number of studies highlighting the importance of green management practices (for example, Cherrafi et al. (2018), Liu et al. (2017), and Ma et al. (2018)). Cooperation with supply chain partners (Cherrafi et al., 2018); environmentally friendly operations (Liu et al., 2017); and internal management and support (e.g., internal efficiency demand) are three key elements of green management practices (Ma et al., 2018).

This research undertakes an evaluation from e-commerce sector in Albania in order to understand the relationship the relationship between green marketing adoption and e-business size. A business would adopt green marketing practices due to internal and external forces, according to Kirchoff et al (2016). Nonetheless, Dardan et al. (2007) contend that the adoption of certain innovations is influenced by the size of the business. Businesses with sufficient resources, such as skilled human resources, technology, and financial resources, will be able to adopt new innovations more quickly and completely than smaller businesses. According to Zhu and Sarkis (2006), organizational size is more important for the adoption of green practices and has an impact on organizational performance (Choi et al,2001). According to some findings, large businesses are in a position to adopt green marketing practices due to their resource capacity (Mitra and Data, 2014). Furthermore, large businesses are more influenced by government pressure to adopt green practices than small businesses (Vachon and Klassen, 2006). Nonetheless, a study conducted in China by Zhu et al (2008) discovered that organization size plays a positive role in the adoption of green practices.

Unfortunately, the findings on the influence of organization size on green marketing adoption are mixed. Furthermore, there is a scarcity of literature and research reports in Albania on the size of businesses and the intensity of green marketing adoption. This inspires me to conduct research on the relationship between business size and green marketing adoption intensity in e-commerce sector in Albania. As a result, the two main purpose of this study are: to determine the level of adoption of green marketing practices and to investigate the relationship between business size and level of green marketing practice adoption. To date, there is no empirical research on the combined characteristics between business size and green marketing adoption intensity in e-commerce sector in Albania. This study will be the first exploratory research in the field.

The following is the structure of the paper: first, a literature review outlines the concepts used and the model developed in this study; second, I explain the methods and data collection process. Finally, I present my analysis of the results and conclusions. Implications and recommendations for further research are also discussed.

II. Literature Review

Because the research topic under consideration in my paper is related to green management practices, green marketing adoption and business size. In the following subsections, I will conduct a critical review of the literature on these topics. The theoretical framework for this current research will be based on five major streams of literature review: (1) The Concept of Green Marketing Practices; (2) Business Size; (3) Resource based theory; and (4) E-commerce sector in Albania and (5) Green Marketing Adoption and Business Size

2.1 The Concept of Green Marketing Practices

According to the American Marketing Association, green marketing refers to the marketing of environmentally friendly products. Thus, green marketing encompasses a wide range of activities, such as product modification, changes to the manufacturing process, packaging changes, and modifying advertising. Environmental marketing and ecological marketing are two other terms that are used interchangeably. Thus, "Green Marketing" refers to a holistic marketing concept in which the production, marketing, consumption, and disposal of products and services are done in a way that is less harmful to the environment. With increasing awareness about the implications of global warming, non-biodegradable solid waste, the harmful impact of pollutants, and so on, both marketers and consumers are becoming increasingly sensitive to the need for a shift to green products and services. While the transition to "green" may appear to be costly in the short term, it will undoubtedly prove to be indispensable and cost-effective in the long run.

Green marketing practices vary, but the majority of them revolve around the traditional marketing four Ps: green product, green pricing, green promotion, and green distribution (Polonsky 1994; Kinoti 2011). Various researchers have reported on various green practices that most businesses have adopted. According to Polonsky (1994), green marketing practices include product modifications, changes to manufacturing methods and processes, and changes to advertising and packaging. To generate attention and demand for sustainable products, effective green marketing practices must be based on green packaging, green branding, labeling, and advertising (Juwaheer et al 2012). Interestingly, Sarkar (2012) agreed that green marketing encompasses a wide range of activities, including product modification, packaging, changes to the manufacturing process, remodeling and developing a new style, and relying on advertisements that promote green consumption. The green marketing practices proposed by Polonsky (1994) and Kinoti (2011) were examined for the purpose of measuring the level of green marketing adoption in this study.

Furthermore, the level of adoption of green marketing practices is determined by the number of practices implemented.

2.2 Business Size

The scale of organization and operations of a business enterprise is referred to as its business size. Depending on their level of development, different countries use different measures of size. The most commonly used indices are total employee count, total investment, and sales turnover. Businesses are classified into four categories in Albania development policy of 2022: micro, small, medium and big enterprises as specified in table 1:

Table 1: Businesses classification in Albania

Classification	Number of employed persons	Annual Sales Revenues (ALL)
Micro-enterprise	1 – 9	A total annual balance not exceeding ALL 10 million
Small Enterprise	10 – 49	A total annual balance not exceeding ALL 50 million
Medium Enterprise	50 -249	A total annual balance not exceeding ALL 250 million
Big Enterprise	Over 250	A total annual turnover grater than ALL 250 million

Source: Own elaboration based on the information generated by <https://www.tatime.gov.al/c/6/legislacioni>.

It should be noted that SMEs are regarded as the engine of innovation and sustainable development. They may be able to solve societal and environmental issues (Kardosa 2012).

Regarding the e-commerce sector in Albania, a serious problem is informatization. Small businesses start with personal, family acquaintances, they start selling basic things and then with the increase in flow forces them to legal register, focus on digital marketing, contract for distribution. As stated by the director of the Albanian E-commerce Association in 2021, every day 17,000 – 20,000 orders are delivered by postal companies to customers, where less than 30% belong to companies operating legally in the market. The biggest challenge remains the formalization of the market, the opening to global markets and the development of this sector according to professional standards. According to QKB the ecommerce sector in Albania is dominated by SMEs

2.3 Resource based theory

According to resource-based theory, in order for a business to be and remain competitive in a market, it must seek out and protect its unique resources (Barney & Warnerfelt, 1995). According to Dowel and Heart (2011), in order to remain competitive, a business must seek, protect, and use both intangible and tangible resources. In that sense, if resources are made available in the required capacity and used in an effective and efficient manner, business success is assured. According to resource-based theory, business characteristics, particularly the availability of critical resources, can influence the levels of green practice adoption (Uhlener et al.2012). This is due to the fact that the available resources will be used to add more unique and inimitable resources, allowing a business to remain powerful and competitive. Recent research suggests that a proactive environmental strategy can help to bridge the gap between a company's environmental capabilities and its competitive advantage (Chan, 2021; Mishra & Yadav, 2021). Higher-order resources, such as accurate business forecasts and strategic planning, can provide a firm with a long-term competitive advantage through its operating resources, which include specialized manufacturing plants, brand names, loyal customers, and patents (Wibbens, 2019). In the context of SMEs, larger firms are more likely to engage in sustainable practices because they have more resources and stakeholder influence than small businesses (Uhlener et al. 2012; Lynch-Wood and Williamson 2014). As a result, the

study draws on theory to consider that a business with sufficient resources has the potential to invest in more unique resources such as green technology, which in turn helps a business to be more competitive and achieve sustainable development. They may be able to solve societal and environmental issues (Kardosa 2012).

2.4 E-commerce Sector in Albania

Online sales have recently increased in Albania. Businesses are selling more online as technology advances and social networks spread, although in an unorganized manner. Both market participants and postal operators report an increase in delivery volume in 2022. Informality and the widespread use of cash in the economy continue to be issues. The major market participants anticipate that the positive performance will continue based on two main arguments. First, they target customers between the ages of 17 and 35 as a target group who return to their online shopping experience. Second, as technology advances and the use of smartphones increases, consumers are becoming more prone to this consumer behavior.

As showed in a survey by statistics office Instat in December 2021, the number of Albanians making online purchases continued to increase in 2021, with 21.4% of the population aged 16-74 saying they had made an online purchase in the preceding 12 months. The main cities in Albania where e-commerce takes place are mainly Tirana, Durres, Elbasani, Korça, Shkodra, Fieri and Vlora. Social networks are widely used by businesses to increase their activity. According to data from Instagram (2021), in just one month, about 90 million accounts have clicked on the post of a certain product to learn more details about it.

Informality is very high in the Albania's online sales. Informality is prevalent among online sales operators, who claim that because of the opportunities provided by online operations, many people avoid fiscal obligations. Most delivery services in Tirana are provided by unlicensed individuals. Cash-on-delivery accounts for nearly 90% of all online sales. All market participants claim that if they only accepted online payments, none of them would be able to compete. The lack of an entry barrier in the e-business has made that a lot of new e-business are being created each day.

According to European E-Commerce Report in 2021, Albania is the country with the lowest percentage of online purchases compared to the countries of the European Union and candidates for membership. According to this report, 85% of respondents stated that they have not made online purchases and 15% that they have made online purchases. Among the candidate countries, Macedonia has the lowest percentage of online purchases after Albania, where only 25% of respondents stated that they made online purchases. In Montenegro, Serbia and Turkey, the percentage of online respondents who stated that they have made online purchases varies from 31 to 34%. The average of respondents in the European Union who stated that they have made online purchases is 67%.

2.5 Green Marketing Adoption and Business Size

The size of the company is one of the internal variables that influence the adoption of green marketing practices. The levels of adoption of green practices are influenced by business characteristics, specifically the availability of critical resources (Uhlener et al.2012). The size of the business influences the adoption of certain innovations (Dardan et al.2007). Companies with sufficient resources, such as skilled human resources, technology, and financial resources, will be able to adopt new innovations more quickly and completely than smaller companies. According to Zhu and Sarkis (2006), organizational size is more important for green practices adoption and has an impact on organizational performance (Choi et al,2001). According to some findings, large businesses are better positioned to adopt green marketing practices due to increased resource capacity (Uhlener et al. 2012; Lynch-Wood & Williamson 2014; Mitra & Data, 2014; and Singh et al. 2014). Furthermore, large businesses, as opposed to small businesses, are more susceptible to government pressure as they adopt green practices (Vachon & Klassen, 2006). Nonetheless, a study conducted in China by Zhu et al (2008) discovered that organization size plays a positive role in the adoption

of green marketing practices. However, from another perspective, a large business will be less benefited by structural inertia, as they are less agile and flexible than small businesses (Sulaiman, et al 2015). Due to its management structure, making decisions takes a long time. Even if small businesses are limited in terms of technology and financial resources, they will be more active and quicker to adopt and meet market demands (Zhu et al, 2006). Furthermore, the findings of the green marketing studies conducted by Ofunya (2012) and Durmaz & Yaşar (2016) show that green marketing adoption is influenced by regulations, customer and consumer pressure, corporate social responsibility, increasing emphasis on environmental issues, firm's reputation, performance, market share, and competitive advantage.

While authors such as Zhu and Sarkis (2006) and Zhu et al (2008) acknowledge that business size influences the level of green marketing adoption, other studies such as Zhu et al (2006) and Vachon & Klassen (2006) argue that small and large businesses have an equal chance of adopting green marketing practices. Thus, the purpose of this research is to determine the level of green marketing adoption among e-businesses and to investigate the impact of business size on green marketing adoption in Albania.

III. Tools and Methodology

The study used a descriptive design with a survey study approach, with data collected from 120 micro, small, medium and big enterprise who have a website or online marketplace in Albania. Simple random sampling from different e-commerce businesses was used, which ensures approximate independence of observations.

The sample was obtained through the use of a purposive sampling technique, which was viable due to the inability to obtain a reliable database from QKB. This source was used to check e-commerce information before conducting a field survey study to test the proposed hypotheses.

This study seeks to answer the following major questions:

Question 1: What is the level of adoption of green marketing?

Question 2: Does the size of the business influence the level of adoption of green marketing?

The size of the e-commerce company was defined based on annual sales revenues (ALL) declare during the survey. According to Baker (2003), the study sample should include people who have access to the information that the research seeks. To avoid complacency, respondents focused on top positions involving their firms' strategic orientation. To achieve the desired results, business owners, marketing managers, and operations managers were used as units of inquiry.

A questionnaire was used to collect data. Data were collected during November 2022 using telephone survey. Following that, data was analyzed, and a chi square was used to test the relationship between the dependent variable (Adoption level of Green Marketing Practices) and the independent variable (Business size). Table 2 presented below represent the characteristics of the sample.

Table 2. The characteristics of the sample

Demographic of the sample	Number of firms (n = 120)	Percent (%)
<i>(a) Firm age</i>		
0–2 years	10	8.4
3– 5 years	43	35.8
6–8 years	37	30.8
9–11 years	18	15
Above 12 years	12	10
<i>(b) Respondents' position</i>		
CEO, Entrepreneurs, Business owners, managers, or other top or middle positions	120	100

<i>(c) Type of industry</i>		
Food & beverage/Agriculture	4	3
Medical devices & pharmaceutical	8	6
Auto parts and Machinery	3	2
Retail/wholesale	58	50
Electronics	25	21
Others	22	18

Source: Own elaboration

IV. Findings

This section includes the findings regarding business size, green marketing adoption level, and the relationship between green marketing adoption and business size.

4.1 Business Size

Business characteristics in terms of size was captured during the study defined by the number of employees and annual sales revenues. The size of the business ranged from Micro, Small, Medium and Large Business. Table 3 shows the number of businesses in their respective business categories. This indicates that the business sizes categories are normally distributed between small, medium and large business therefore was suitable for me to run a chi square test against the level of adoption (high and low) to test its association.

Table 3. Business Size

Business Size	Frequency	Percent
Micro Business	3	2.5
Small Business	40	33.3
Medium Business	39	32.5
Large Business	38	31.7
Total	120	100.0

Source: Own elaboration

4.2 Adoption of Green Marketing Practices

Respondents from e-commerce sector were asked to indicate whether they adopted or did not adopt the twelve practices recommended by Polonsky (1994) and Kinoti (2011) in order to establish the set of green marketing practices in their business. Table 4 shows the composition of the twelve green marketing practices in Albania e-commerce sector.

Table 4. Green Marketing Practices Composition by Adoption Counts

Green Marketing Practices	Status	Count(n*)
Production of eco-friendly products	Practicing	5
	Not Practicing	115
Use of eco-friendly Packages	Practicing	71
	Not Practicing	49
Water recycling	Practicing	0
	Not Practicing	120
Use of Clean energy/Renewable (gas, biogas, solar etc.)	Practicing	0
	Not Practicing	120
Charging higher Price for Green Products	Practicing	112
	Not Practicing	8
Green label usage	Practicing	55

	Not Practicing	65
Promotes Green Lifestyle	Practicing	71
	Not Practicing	49
Promotes the Benefits of Green Products	Practicing	75
	Not Practicing	45
Promotes Green Image of the Product	Practicing	53
	Not Practicing	67
Reverse Channel system (Collecting wastes for recycling)	Practicing	2
	Not Practicing	118
Use of Economic and energy efficiency Transport	Practicing	29
	Not Practicing	81
Use of Secondary Packages (Containers)	Practicing	2
	Not Practicing	118

*n-Indicates the number of e-commerce company who adopted and those who did not adopt.

Source: Own elaboration

According to my research findings showed in Table 4, many businesses adopted few green marketing practices because only 5% of the e-commerce businesses produced at least one green product, 59.2% of the e-commerce businesses used green packaging. Nonetheless, many businesses did not adopt green marketing practices such as the use of secondary packages, reverse channel systems, water recycling (0% of businesses), and the use of renewable energy. Because of the high cost of green technology and the low demand for green products, most businesses did not adopt these green marketing practices.

4.3 Green Marketing Practices Adoption

My study's goal was to determine the level of Green Marketing Practice Adoption in e-commerce sector in Albania. The extent of adoption was measured by the number of practices adopted out of 12 practices, as shown in Table 4, with less than or equal to six practices considered low, and 7 to 12 practices considered high, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Adoption Frequency Level in Percentage

Business Size	Frequency	Percent
Low Extent (≤ 6 Practices)	103	86 %
High Extent (7 -12 Practices)	27	14 %
Total	120	100 %

Source: Own elaboration

According to my findings, 103/120 businesses (86%) had adopted at least one to six practices which is consider low extent of adoption), while 27/120 businesses (14%) had adopted seven to twelve practices which is consider higher extent. As a result, the level of adoption of green marketing practices among e-commerce businesses in Albania was low, with 86 percent of businesses adopting less than 7 practices of the twelve practices tested. This could be due to capital constraints and low government incentives to favor company that uses green practices.

4.4 The Relationship between Business Size and Adoption Level of Green Marketing

My objective was to identify a link between business size and green marketing adoption level. The two variables, business size and level of adoption, were then tested. The size of the business was determined by the capital invested, as shown in table 2, and the level of adoption was determined by the number of green marketing practices implemented, as shown in table 3 above. The chi square test of independence output

from SPSS. The chi square of independence test was used to determine the relationship between business size and adoption level. No cell had a count that was less than 5. Because the assumption was met, the minimum expected count was 12.35. Because the P-value is 0.025, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the relationship between business size and adoption level of green marketing practices is significant. As a result, the size of a business and the level of green marketing adoption are not independent. Also, it is showed the business size influences the adoption level at the medium level of Phi Value.258.

V. Conclusions and Recommendations

Green Marketing is critical to saving the world from pollution. According to the findings, various green marketing practices were implemented. Few of them were widely used by e-commerce businesses. Green product, use of eco-friendly packaging, and green promotion (promoting a green lifestyle) were discovered to be adopted by many businesses when compared to others. However, green marketing practices such as green process (water recycling, use of green energy), and green place (use of secondary packaging) were found to be less adopted, as fewer businesses adopted these practices than others. Less adopted practices may be influenced by financial factors, as installing green technology is expensive (Kinoti, 2011).

Furthermore, it was discovered that the level of adoption of green marketing practices was low because most businesses adopted relatively few practices, which were less than or equal to six. Medium businesses (those with more capital than small and micro businesses) were found to adopt more practices than small and micro businesses. This could be due to the financial power that medium-sized businesses have, as Dardan (2007) contends that businesses with sufficient capital have a better chance of going green than those with insufficient capital due to the initial green technology costs associated with going green.

I have discovered also a link between business size and the level of adoption of green marketing practices, with large businesses adopting more practices than medium, small and micro e-commerce businesses. My findings appear to support earlier studies such as Dardan (2007), Uhlener et al (2012), Lynch-Wood and Williamson (2014), Mitra and Data (2014), and Singh et al (2014), which report that a business with adequate resources, including large capital, has a better chance of going green than one with insufficient resources. This is due to the initial financial resources that must be invested at the beginning. Furthermore, it should be noted that the study only focused on e-commerce sector in Albania. Albanian companies cannot report and update information on the performance and compliance of their environmental activities unless green management practices are implemented. Green management for small businesses may instead take the form of other practices such as the 3 R concept (Reduce-Reuse-Recycle), less energy usage, and waste minimization. As a result, green initiatives and management can stimulate innovation and reveal new sources of new products and revenue.

The findings are limited to e-commerce sector and could be applied even in other sector in the Albanian industry. I encourage future research into multilevel time series models with applications to repeated measures data. In order to specify causality by reaching pre- and post-behavioral interpretation. Finally, due to the nature of green management practices, I cannot test them in a nonlinear relationship. Future research could use the curvilinear function to assess the effectiveness of green management practices in e-commerce sector in Albania.

VI. References

- [1] Kotler, P., Kartajaya, H., & Setiawan, I., (2021) *Marketing 5.0: Technology for Humanity*, John Wiley & Sons, ISBN: 1119668514, 9781119668510
- [1] Mohajan, H., (2012) *Importance of Green Marketing at Present and Future: Importance of Green Marketing*, LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, ISBN: 978-3659314346
- [2] Campbell, J. (2007). Why would corporations behave in socially responsible ways? An institutional theory of corporate social responsibility. *Acad. Management. Rev.* 32(3), 946–967.

- [2] Darnall, N., Henriques, I., & Sadorsky, P. (2010). Adopting proactive environmental strategy: The influence of stakeholders and firm size. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(6), 1072–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2009.00873.x>
- [2] Durmaz, Y., & Yaşar, H. V. (2016). Green Marketing and Benefits to Business. *Business and Management Studies*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.11114/bms.v2i2.1624>
- [2] Huang, X. X., Hu, Z. P., Liu, C. S., Yu, D. J., & Yu, L. F. (2016). The relationships between regulatory and customer pressure, green organizational responses, and green innovation performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 3423–3433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.10.106>
- [2] Gupta, S., Soni, U., & Kumar, G. (2019). Green supplier selection using multi-criterion decision making under fuzzy environment: A case study in automotive industry. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 136, 663–680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.07.038>
- [2] Kardosa M (2012) The Relationship between Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Sustainable Development. *Research on European Union Countries, Procedia Economics and Finance* 3,1030 – 1035.
- [2] King, P. (2000). Gaining competitive advantage through environmental management. *Eco-Management and Auditing*, 3(2), 24–25. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1099-0925\(199607\)3:2<76::aid-ema43>3.0.co;2-p](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1099-0925(199607)3:2<76::aid-ema43>3.0.co;2-p)
- [2] Kimario, J. (2014). Influence of customer demand and green product innovation on firm's performance. A case of food processing firms in Tanzania. *Business management review journal*, 4 (2): 43-55.
- [2] Kinoti, M. (2011). Green marketing Intervention Strategies and Sustainable Development: A Conceptual Paper. *International Journal of Business and Social Science Vol. 2 No. 23*.
- [2] Liu, Y., Zhu, Q., & Seuring, S. (2017). Linking capabilities to green operations strategies: The moderating role of corporate environmental proactivity. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 187, 182–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2017.03.007>
- [2] Lin, W. L., Cheah, J. H., Azali, M., Ho, J. A., & Yip, N. (2019). Does firm size matter? Evidence on the impact of the green innovation strategy on corporate financial performance in the automotive sector. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 974–988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.214>
- [2] Lun, Y. H. V., Lai, K., Wong, C. W. Y., & Cheng, T. C. E. (2016). Green management practices. *Green Shipping Management*, 45–59. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-26482-0_4
- [2] Peng, Y. S., & Lin, S. S. (2008). Local responsiveness pressure, subsidiary resources, green management adoption and subsidiary's performance: Evidence from taiwanese manufactures. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 79(1–2), 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9382-8>
- [2] Polonsky, M. J. (2001). Re-evaluating Green marketing: A Strategic Approach. *Business Horizons*, Vol.44 Issue 5, pg.10, pg.21.
- [2] Robert, D (2011). Green Marketing Theory, Practice and Strategies: 1st Indian Edition. *India Centage Learning Publishers*
- [2] Sarkar, A. N. (2012). Green Branding and Eco-innovations for Evolving a Sustainable Green Marketing Strategy. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 8(1), 39–58. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2319510X1200800106>
- [2] Sirén, C., Hakala, H., Wincent, J., & Grichnik, D. (2017). Breaking the routines: Entrepreneurial orientation, strategic learning, firm size, and age. *Long Range Planning*, 50(2), 145–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2016.09.005>
- [2] Uhlaner, Lorraine, Marta Berent-Braun, Ronald Jeurissen, and Gerrit Wit. 2012. “Beyond Size: Predicting Engagement in Environmental Management Practices of Dutch SMEs.” *Journal of Business Ethics* 109 (4): 411–429. doi:10.1007/s10551-011-1137-x.107
- [3] Foxon, T., & Andersen, M. M. (2009). The greening of innovation systems for eco-innovation – Towards an evolutionary climate mitigation policy. *DRUID Summer Conference – Innovation, Strategy and Knowledge*. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- [4] European Environment Agency (2020), *The European environment — state and outlook 2020: Knowledge for transition to a sustainable Europe*, <http://europa.eu>, ISBN 978-92-9480-090-9, doi: 10.2800/96749
- [4] Eurostat (2022) *EUROPEAN E-COMMERCE REPORT 2022*, https://ecommerce-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/CEI2022_FullVersion_LIGHT_v2.pdf
- [4] Eurostat (2022) *E-commerce statistics for individuals*
- [4] INSTAT (2021), *Urban Solid Waste, 2021*, http://www.instat.gov.al/media/10524/urban-solid-waste-2021_.pdf
- [4] IQAir (2021), *World Air Quality Report: Region and City Ranking*, <https://www.iqair.com/world-air-quality-report>